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FROM CLINICAL PRESENTATION TO GENETIC DIAGNOSIS: A CASE REPORT OF ADULT X-LINKED HYPOPHOSPHATEMIC RICKETS

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Abstract: *The article presents a clinical case of stepwise diagnosis of a rare orphan disease, X-linked hypophosphatemic rickets (XLH), confirmed by genetic testing. X-linked dominant hypophosphatemic rickets (XLH) is a hereditary orphan disorder characterized by impaired bone mineralization due to renal phosphate wasting caused by mutations in the PHEX gene.*

Keywords: *Hypophosphatemic rickets, clinical case, X-linked hypophosphatemia (XLH)*

A 46-year-old female patient (Patient A) presented to her local outpatient clinic with complaints of impaired mobility, pain in both large and small joints, lower back pain, and muscle weakness. These symptoms had been present since the age of 5 years. At the age of 6 years, she was diagnosed with “rheumatism.” At that time, bowing deformity of the lower extremities and growth retardation were also noted. According to the patient, her mother had a similar deformity of the lower limbs. Furthermore, the patient’s 11-year-old son had previously been diagnosed with hypochondroplasia based on severe lower limb deformities, restricted mobility, pain in the hip and knee joints, and short stature.

Fig. 1 Patient A.

Physical examination revealed a height of 132 cm and a body weight of 31 kg. The patient exhibited genu varum (bow-leg deformity) of both lower extremities and thoracic kyphosis. Laboratory investigations demonstrated persistent hypophosphatemia, with serum phosphate levels ranging from 0.44 to 0.95 mmol/L (reference range: 1.45–1.78 mmol/L). Hypocalcemia was also detected, with serum calcium levels as low as 2.0 mmol/L (reference range: 2.15–2.50 mmol/L). The serum concentration of 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D] was decreased to 24.32 ng/mL (reference range: 30–100 ng/mL), while alkaline phosphatase activity was elevated to 110 U/L (reference range: 0–104 U/L). Serum creatinine and urea concentrations remained within normal limits.

Following consultations with a nephrologist and an endocrinologist, and considering the characteristic clinical and laboratory findings, phosphate-

wasting osteomalacia was suspected. Tubular reabsorption of phosphate (TRP) was calculated and found to be 0.40 (reference range: 1.15–2.44). Urinary calcium excretion was 0.37 mmol/L (reference range: 2.50–8.0 mmol/L), and urinary phosphate excretion was 0.44 mmol/L (reference range: 0.81–1.45 mmol/L).

Pedigree analysis revealed familial aggregation of clinical features consistent with XLH.

The patient's mother (generation I) had a history of short stature, lower limb deformities, and chronic musculoskeletal pain suggestive of hypophosphatemic rickets. Genetic testing was performed in the proband (generation II, Patient A). The proband's son (generation III) had previously undergone genetic testing, which confirmed the diagnosis of X-linked hypophosphatemic rickets. Thus, the pedigree demonstrated vertical transmission of the disease through the maternal line.

To confirm a hereditary form of osteomalacia, genetic testing was performed in Patient A. DNA samples were analyzed to identify pathogenic variants within the coding regions of the PHEX gene.

Fig 2. Structure of the PHEX gene

Mutations in the PHEX gene disrupt phosphate reabsorption in the renal tubules and impair intestinal phosphate absorption, resulting in excessive phosphate loss and chronic hypophosphatemia. Genetic analysis revealed the presence of the c.1768+1G>T variant in Patient A. This variant is absent from control populations and has previously been reported in patients with hypophosphatemic rickets in the heterozygous state (PMID: 30607568). Based on the available evidence, the identified variant was classified as pathogenic. Variant interpretation was performed according to the recommendations of the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG) and the Sherlock framework for next-generation sequencing data interpretation.

Prior to genetic confirmation of the diagnosis, Patient A had been managed under several alternative diagnoses, including Legg–Calvé–Perthes disease, undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia, bilateral coxarthrosis, and chondrodysplasia. The patient received calcium supplementation and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) without significant clinical improvement.

Following confirmation of XLH through genetic testing and considering the patient's age and laboratory findings, treatment with alfacalcidol at a dose of 1 µg/day and vitamin D at 5,000 IU/day was initiated. During follow-up, the patient reported a reduction in pain intensity and improvement in muscle strength.

Currently, burosumab, a monoclonal antibody targeting fibroblast growth factor 23 (FGF23), has been developed for the treatment of XLH and is approved for use in both adults and children aged six months and older. However, burosumab is not currently registered in the Republic of Kazakhstan. The decision to initiate burosumab therapy in adults who have achieved final height should be based on disease severity, the risk of complications, the presence of existing complications, and the patient's prior treatment history. Continuous treatment remains essential for achieving optimal therapeutic outcomes and improving the quality of life of patients with XLH.

Conclusion

The estimated incidence of X-linked hypophosphatemia is approximately 3.9 cases per 100,000 live births. In Kazakhstan, 30 cases of XLH were registered in 2025, including 25 pediatric and 5

adult patients. Early diagnosis of this disorder is crucial for preventing severe complications. The similarity of clinical manifestations among various forms of hereditary rickets is one of the major reasons for delayed diagnosis, highlighting the need for continuous improvement of physicians' knowledge regarding inherited skeletal disorders.

The challenges associated with diagnosing XLH are largely attributable to the lack of routine serum phosphate testing and limited awareness of the disease among healthcare professionals. Genetic testing plays a pivotal role in establishing the diagnosis and enabling timely initiation of targeted therapy, ultimately leading to substantial improvements in patient outcomes and quality of life.

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